

The economic impact potential of airborne wind energy in Germany

A study for Airborne Wind Europe

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1. Introduction

Airborne wind energy (AWE) systems use wings or kites, typically attached by a tether to a ground station, to harness wind energy at altitudes of up to 750 metres. At these altitudes, wind speeds are higher and conditions are more stable than at the altitudes typically reached by wind turbines. With better wind availability, significantly lower material requirements and easier logistics compared to wind turbines, AWE is an important complementary technology to traditional wind and solar energy technologies.

Although AWE is still in the early stages of deployment, it is considered to have strong potential for boosting Europe's competitiveness, as many AWE developers and start-ups are currently based in Europe, including Germany. Some steps have been taken by policy makers in Germany to acknowledge and promote AWE. For example, the technology was included in the 2024 revision of the German Renewable Energy Act (EEG), and the coalition agreement of the new German government (CDU, CSU & SPD 2025) pledges to support AWE as one of the innovative green technologies. However, awareness of AWE and the technology's economic benefits remains relatively low so far.

To address this knowledge gap and inform policymakers and the public about the opportunities associated with AWE and the production of AWE systems in Germany, this study assesses the potential economic impact of developing AWE in Germany. This study does not project AWE growth or set a target to be met; rather, it explores the potential economic benefits that Germany could reap by enabling the development of the AWE industry and possibly securing a leadership position in this emerging field.

In the next section, we provide an overview of AWE technologies. In Section 3, we outline our methodological approach for assessing the economic impact of AWE and provide an estimate of the potential investment needs per gigawatt (GW) of AWE capacity. We also consider the economic impact of AWE investments along the value chain. Next, we discuss the potential for scaling up AWE and its possible contribution to the industrial landscape, regional value chains, innovation ecosystem and energy security in Germany.

2. AWE technologies

Unlike established three-bladed horizontal axis wind turbines, airborne wind energy cannot be described as a single technology. Rather, AWE technologies comprise a diverse set of design concepts

that differ in how energy is captured, converted and delivered to the grid. Figure 2-1 illustrates this with a selection of AWE devices. The various designs influence the technical performance, as well as the implications for value chains and deployment strategies. The main distinctions can be drawn along three dimensions: the location of power generation, the flight pattern and the type of wing employed.

Figure 2-1: A selection of AWE devices in flight

Source: Airborne Wind Europe.

In terms of power generation, AWE systems can be classified as ground-gen technologies, which produce electricity at the ground station, or fly-gen technologies, which position generators directly on the airborne device. Regarding the flight trajectory of the kite, three types can be distinguished: crosswind systems (most common), tether-aligned systems, and rotational systems. Regarding the design of the airborne wing or kite, AWE systems can use soft or semi-rigid kites, or rigid wings. Further details on the various technologies are provided in Annex A.

3. Economic impact of potential investments in AWE

3.1 Methodology and data

Significant uncertainties remain about how AWE will develop in Germany and worldwide in the coming years, and estimates of how much AWE capacity can be installed in Germany by 2035 vary considerably (see Section 4.1 for more details). Therefore, we assess the macroeconomic impact of the investment

required for each gigawatt (GW) of installed capacity in Germany, before discussing the overall economic impact depending on the capacity addition scenario.¹

For the investment requirement, we use data from AWE companies. Five companies have provided information on

- their projected capacity additions until 2035;
- their projected employment until 2035;
- the current and projected cost of their AWE technology;
- the cost structure of their AWE technology by component.

As all five companies represent different technologies, the total cost, employment and cost structure per GW of capacity were calculated as a weighted average of all five technologies. By doing this, the study operates with an 'average' technology in the mix that could be present in the market in future, including, for example, a mixture of soft, semi-rigid and rigid kites. The total projected installed capacity is also used as one of the capacity addition scenarios in the discussion below. **As the study aims to evaluate the potential economic impact of establishing the AWE industry in Germany, it is assumed that AWE installations are assembled in Germany.** However, the components may be imported from other countries. We use official German statistics to estimate import quotas for the relevant sectors.

We then use input-output (IO) modelling to quantify the potential economic impact of AWE investment in terms of gross value added and employment:

- **Gross value added** along the entire value chain is the most important measure to assess the economic performance of an industry or economy. Gross value added is defined as output minus intermediate inputs. Its main components are labour and capital incomes, i.e. wages and profits.
- **Employment effect:** The number of persons employed comprises all employees, persons in marginal employment as well as self-employed and unpaid family workers, independently of the number of hours worked.

More precisely, the quantitative economic IO analysis enables us to analyse the interdependencies between sectors within the German economy. By tracing these linkages, we can identify supply chains associated with potential AWE investments in Germany. This allows us to quantify the direct, indirect and induced economic effects. Figure 3-1 illustrates the total economic effects of AWE investments in Germany.

¹ For comparison, 1 GW capacity is equivalent to around 200 modern onshore wind turbines.

Figure 3-1: Total effects of AWE investments as the sum of direct, indirect and induced effects

Source: DIW Econ.

- **Direct effects** from AWE investments will be created through installation and production activities in Germany, i.e. value added (labour and capital income) and the number of employed persons in AWE companies.
- AWE investments will create **indirect effects** when inputs required for production and installation of AWE systems, e.g. services, machinery and equipment, are purchased. This demand creates again value added and employment among suppliers and their suppliers up the value chain, which thus can be indirectly linked to AWE investments. This way, the initial impulse of investments in Germany is multiplied.
- **Induced effects** are generated, when labour and capital income of AWE developers and producers (direct effect) and their suppliers (indirect effect) is spent on other goods and services.

Value-added along the value chain: Figure 3-2 shows how direct and indirect value-added effects are created throughout the value chain of an AWE investment. When AWE developers install their systems, they incur labour costs, which constitute direct value added.² They also have to purchase components for the system, such as electronic equipment, machinery, and kite materials. The cost of these components is split between the value added by the component producer and the cost of intermediate products further up the value chain. For example, a producer of electronic equipment would increase demand for electronic products, metal products and transport services. Thus, investment in an AWE system creates additional demand for goods and services along the entire production chain. A certain

² The profits of AWE developers would also constitute direct value added. However, as we have no information on expected profits and most AWE developers are start-ups, we have implicitly excluded them from our calculations.

proportion of the resulting additional production constitutes incomes, i.e. value added, which can be indirectly linked to the AWE investment. Depending on the investment structure and the structure of the economy, these additional incomes may cumulate to amounts comparable to the investment itself.

Figure 3-2: Creation of indirect value added along the value chain

Source: DIW Econ.

The effects are assessed using an economic impact model compiled by DIW Econ. This model is based on detailed IO tables that reflect the interconnections within a national economy, including the product flows between the national economy and the rest of the world. In Germany, IO accounts are compiled centrally at the Federal Statistical Office (Destatis). The German IO table provides key information on how different sectors supply and demand inputs from other sectors in the economy. Therefore, the IO model is a particularly suitable tool for analysing the overall economic impact of AWE investments in Germany, while considering the interdependences among different sectors in Germany. The most recent IO table available at the time of modelling was from 2021.

3.2 Investment in AWE

AWE companies expect the cost of their technologies to fall significantly in the coming years, through both scaling up and learning effects. **In fact, they expect their technologies to reach cost parity with wind turbines, or even to become more cost-efficient, by 2035.**³ The estimated average investment

³ The current investment cost of onshore wind turbines ranges between 1300 and 1900 EUR/kW in Germany (Kost, et al. 2024). The European data suggest that the investment cost is expected to fall by another around 5% by 2035 (Danish Energy Agency 2024).

cost across different AWE technologies for the period 2025–2035 is around 1665 EUR/kW, or almost EUR 1.7 billion per GW of installed capacity. Intermediate goods (AWE system components, installation costs, etc.) account for the majority of the total cost, while the labour cost, which constitutes direct value added, represents 11% of the total cost (see Figure 3-3). Considering the potential import of components, it is estimated that around 77% of the investment would be sourced directly in Germany.

Figure 3-3: Total investment for 1 GW AWE capacity and cost share of Germany, EUR million

Source: DIW Econ.

Figure 3-4 shows how the costs of intermediate goods for AWE systems are distributed across German economic sectors, using the IO table classification. The three main cost components are: electrical equipment (including electronics and power controls); machinery (including winches and other mechanical parts); and other transport equipment (including rigid wings, rigid structures of semi-rigid wings, and rotors, if applicable)⁴. Together, these components represent almost two-thirds of intermediate goods and services. Other significant cost components include metal products (e.g. the body of the ground station and the landing platform), civil engineering activities (e.g. construction and preparatory works on the platform, extension of power lines for grid connection where applicable), specialised construction activities (e.g. the actual cabling and connection of the system to the grid), engineering activities (e.g. planning and permitting), computers (e.g. automation systems/board computers), insurance costs, chemical products (e.g. the tether, usually made of polyethylene fibres) and textile products (e.g. soft kites or textile covers for semi-rigid kites).

⁴ Rigid wings, rigid structures of semi-rigid wings, and rotors of airborne devices fall under “manufacture of air and spacecraft and related machinery”, i.e. aviation equipment, in the European classification of economic activities (NACE). As such they fall under the larger sector of “other transport equipment” in the IO table classification.

Figure 3-4: Cost structure of AWE investment by IO sector

Source: DIW Econ.

3.3 Economic impacts of AWE investment

If AWE systems are manufactured in Germany, producing and installing 1 GW of AWE capacity in Germany could generate approximately EUR 1.3 billion in direct, indirect and induced gross value added (see Figure 3-5, left panel). As described above, the direct effects refer to value added created by the AWE companies, when they (potentially) assemble and install the systems. Indirect effects refer to the production and delivery of all purchased components and any third-party services provided to AWE companies for planning, installation, etc. The indirect effects also include demand effects further up the value chain.⁵ The induced effects refer to re-spending of the generated incomes.

Due to the significant proportion of intermediate goods and services in AWE investment, the indirect incomes, which are generated through demand for goods and services along the value chain, dominate the total effect. These indirectly generated incomes are also the main driver of the high induced effects. Consequently, the direct effect, i.e. the estimated direct labour costs in AWE companies, accounts for only around 13% of the total.

Additionally, expanding 1 GW of AWE capacity could generate up to 13,260 jobs, primarily within the supply chain and through spending generated income (Figure 3-5, right panel). With around 650 employees per GW of capacity, direct employment requirements at AWE companies are small

⁵ Note that AWE companies may be involved in the installation and production processes to varying degrees. In some cases, they may focus primarily on development and system planning, outsourcing most of the production and installation activities. Therefore, the distinction in modelling between the direct effects at AWE companies and the indirect effects with suppliers does not indicate how the effects are split between installation and production activities. This also applies to employment effects.

compared to the indirect and induced effects and represent just 5% of the total impact. This means that if the AWE industry were to be based in Germany, its economic impact would extend well beyond its own operations.

Figure 3-5: Value added and employment effects per 1 GW of AWE capacity

Source: DIW Econ.

To put these numbers into perspective, it is interesting to compare the employment effects with the benchmarks of a well-established wind industry. Cameron and van der Zwaan (2015) suggest that the installation of conventional onshore wind turbines requires between 500 and 6,700 employees per GW of capacity (median: 2,000 employees), although this figure may have decreased somewhat over the past decade due to economies of scale and learning effects. **With 650 employees, AWE's direct employment effect is at the lower end of the range for conventional wind turbine installation.** This is unsurprising given that AWE systems do not require extensive preparatory work such as foundation construction, tower erection or high-altitude assembly.⁶

The production of AWE systems is estimated to generate around 5,000 jobs per GW capacity, representing the first-order indirect effect. This accounts for a significant proportion of the total indirect impact, with an additional 2,740 jobs emerging further up the value chain (compare Figure 3-5 above). Cameron and van der Zwaan (2015) estimate that the manufacturing of conventional wind turbines creates between 2,700 and 12,500 jobs, with a median of 4,000. However, our estimate, based on German statistics and cost data from Kost et al. (2024), suggests a higher figure for Germany of just over 6,400 employees. **Employment in the production of AWE systems is somewhat lower than in the production of wind turbines in Germany, and is well within the range suggested in the literature.** As with installation employment, a lower employment factor than that for conventional

⁶ However, note that, as discussed above, the direct effect is only a rough approximation of installation employment.

wind turbines is expected given that AWE systems have significantly fewer and/or smaller parts, allowing for a higher degree of automation in the manufacturing process. As production scales up, the gap with conventional wind turbines is expected to widen further.

4. Discussion of AWE roll-out

4.1 Potential impact of AWE scale-up

It is still uncertain how quickly the expansion of airborne wind energy will progress in the near future, and there are a lot of market and institutional factors that can influence its development. We considered two approaches to estimating the potential capacity additions until 2035: based on the historical data on the scale-up of conventional wind turbines and based directly on AWE companies' projections.

The first approach assumes that the scale-up of AWE will follow the same path as conventional wind energy (wind turbines) followed since the mid-1980s. We used data from the International Renewable Energy Agency (downloaded from Our World in Data (2025)) to approximate the curve of capacity additions between 2000 and 2023, taking into account the slow start between 1985 and 2000 (BVG Associates 2022). We then applied this curve to estimate the potential AWE capacity additions until 2035. Such estimates are, however, sensitive to assumptions, especially when the scaling is expected to speed up with time. **If 2025 is assumed as a starting year for AWE development, around 2.3 GW of installed capacity could be achieved in Germany by 2035.**⁷ Given that there have been land-based AWE installations already around 2020, taking 2020 as a starting year instead yields 6.6 GW cumulative installed capacity by 2035 (see Figure 4-1). We consider this as the upper limit for the historical data-based approach.

Aggregating the AWE companies' projections on their market growth yields a slower start but an even higher cumulative installed capacity of approximately 7.8 GW by 2035. This more optimistic view is based, among other things, on the growing interest in renewable technologies, which was not present in the early years of conventional wind turbine development. In particular, Germany aims to completely decarbonise its power system by 2035. Given that Germany abandoned nuclear power, this means that power generation would have to be 100% renewable by then. With AWE's benefits of higher supply stability and flexibility (see Section 4.2 below for more details), it is therefore not

⁷ In this more conservative estimate, the cumulative world capacity would reach around 5.9 GW by 2035, which is close to previous calculations (BVG Associates 2022).

implausible that AWE can scale up faster, provided that there are favourable incentive structures and institutional framework.

Figure 4-1: Scenarios of cumulative installed capacity development in Germany by 2035, GW

Source: DIW Econ.

Moreover, keeping in mind the overall industrial capacity and the nascent AWE production in Germany, it also **appears plausible that manufacturing capacities could potentially be scaled up to serve the production demand fuelled by such AWE expansion**. In fact, some AWE companies report that they are seeking to focus on a few or just one country for AWE roll-out during early market development. With the first pilot projects in place, Germany currently represents one of the potential first-mover markets, although there is also a significant risk that some other country will engage faster and Germany ends up lagging behind in the AWE market. As such, Germany will be facing competition from other markets, including growing interest in AWE in China (China Daily 2024, Yuhan 2025). Attracting the industry to Germany would therefore require framework conditions that facilitate access to finance and scaling-up of the domestic supply chain.

Applying the different deployment projections to the economic impacts per 1 GW of AWE capacity, as estimated in Section 3.3, shows that **the cumulative potential for value added creation lies between EUR 3.1 billion and EUR 10.5 billion over the next ten years**. AWE scale-up could also generate 30,600-104,300 job-years during this period. However, the estimate of job-years does not consider that a position created by new installations in early 2026 can be secured through future AWE deployment throughout the modelling period. Consequently, one job could account for ten job-years between 2026 and 2035. Taking the annual average, **AWE deployment could support around 3,100-10,400 direct, indirect and induced jobs, depending on the expansion scenario**. The upper end of this range is close to the total number of jobs estimated for the onshore wind energy sector (including both installation

and operation of wind turbines) across the entire state of Schleswig-Holstein, one of the wind-richest German regions, in 2018 (about 11,900 direct, indirect and induced jobs) (DIW Econ 2020).

Figure 4-2: Value and employment creation potential by deployment scenario

Source: DIW Econ.

In this context, it should be noted that the focus of this study is the potential production of AWE systems for installation in Germany. In other words, **the study begins with the aim of achieving a certain capacity, assumes that this capacity is produced domestically, and quantifies the economic impact of the respective investment in Germany.** If the systems were imported for installation in Germany, the domestic economic impacts would be limited to installation costs and related value chain effects.

Similarly, a scenario in which production is set up and scaled up to cover exports of AWE systems to other markets was beyond the scope of the analysis, as this would require a different approach to quantification, taking a producer cost perspective. Scaling production beyond domestic AWE capacity to serve additional markets would correspondingly provide stronger impulses to domestic value chains. Some of the companies that provided data for this study also stated their expected global installed capacity by 2035. For those who provided this information, the German market share varied between 36% and 70%. Locating production facilities for both domestic and foreign markets in one place would allow for greater economies of scale during the early stages of AWE development. **If AWE companies were to locate production for domestic and foreign sales in Germany, the value chain effects could be substantially increased compared to production for the German market only,** as analysed in this study. However, it should be noted that the increase will not be directly proportional

to capacity, as certain activities, such as planning and installation, will be performed directly in the foreign market to at least some extent.

4.2 Potential contribution beyond AWE investment

AWE is an innovative renewable energy technology with the potential to strengthen Germany's domestic value chains and enhance the resilience and security of its electricity system. Unlike conventional onshore and offshore wind turbines, which rely on tall towers and fixed blades, AWE uses tethered kites or airborne structures to harness stronger and more consistent winds at higher altitudes. This technological approach offers industrial opportunities and system-level advantages, making it a valuable addition to Germany's energy transition strategy. This section examines the contribution of AWE to regional value chains, industrial and innovation landscape in Germany in more detail and explores how it can improve energy security as the country transitions to a climate-neutral electricity system.

4.2.1 Industrial landscape and regional value chains

Like traditional wind turbines and solar PV, AWE systems are highly decentralised. The demand for skilled personnel in installation and maintenance can therefore **support regional economic development, with value creation and employment opportunities also in rural areas**, where AWE systems are likely to be deployed. Moreover, unlike, e.g., in the production of solar panels in China, the nascent AWE industry does not yet have a clear dominant manufacturing location or country yet. This implies that AWE development could potentially support industrial diversification in the production of clean energy technologies, advanced materials, electronics and machinery in Germany.

As shown in section 3.2, key supply sectors for AWE systems are electrical components, machinery, and transport equipment. **All three sectors have a strong standing in Germany, creating a good basis for developing domestic value chains for the AWE industry.** For example, there are several clusters of electronics industry in Germany, including a large and growing "Silicon Saxony" cluster around Dresden, where several chip factories are being built (Infineon 2025, Weckbrodt 2024). The sector therefore is well positioned to support the AWE industry's needs for advanced power electronics, grid integration solutions, and sophisticated control systems. Additionally, Germany's aerospace and automotive industries offer advanced materials knowledge, lightweight design capabilities, and high-performance manufacturing methods, all of which could support the production of AWE kites and wings.

The economic contribution of AWE systems extends beyond their initial production and installation. Throughout their technical lifetime, AWE systems generate added value and employment through operation and maintenance.

Compared to conventional wind turbines, AWE systems have somewhat higher maintenance requirements, primarily due to wear and tear of kites and tethers. The tether, which experiences significant mechanical stress, needs replacing every two years, although this may vary depending on the intensity of strain. Importantly, replacements can often be carried out by section rather than for the entire tether, increasing efficiency and reducing waste (Wilhelm 2018, Coutinho 2024). Similarly, the soft covers of semi-rigid and soft kites are replaced annually, though soft kites allow for the partial replacement of specific components (Coutinho 2024). The exoskeletons of semi-rigid kites also have a that is shorter than that of the entire AWE system (Coutinho 2024).

Taken together, **these replacement cycles generate stable, recurring demand for high-tech materials, textiles and engineering services**. If these materials and services are sourced domestically, they represent a significant opportunity for German industries to secure long-term supply contracts and service agreements. In this sense, AWE installations are ongoing drivers of industrial activity, generating repeat orders, supporting specialised SMEs and reinforcing Germany's broader industrial ecosystem, not merely capital investments. Furthermore, replacing components regularly enables the installation of the latest generation of equipment, essentially allowing for regular repowering and increasing system efficiency.

4.2.2 Innovation

There are several dimensions, along which AWE could contribute to Germany's innovation landscape:

- cross-sectoral innovation,
- applied research and industry research partnerships,
- SME and start-up ecosystems,
- digitalisation and AI.

AWE technologies lie at the intersection of the aerospace, energy, advanced materials and digital control systems sectors. They combine expertise in lightweight structures and aerodynamics from the aerospace sector, power generation technologies and grid integration from the energy sector, and products from the electronics and IT sectors for autonomous control and system optimisation. These technologies take into account weather conditions, grid integration, and the potential need for evasive manoeuvres when sharing airspace with other aircraft. Advancements in these technologies can also

support spillovers into other sectors, such as autonomous driving and drone technologies, as well as the aerospace sector.

AWE technologies are now reaching demonstration stages and moving towards commercialisation, so **AWE projects are often a product of industry and academic cooperation.** These demonstration projects are often funded by national or European innovation funds. One example from Germany is a partnership between the AWE developer SkySails Power, the energy company EnBW, the Institute for Drive Systems and Power Electronics at Leibniz University Hannover, and the offshore wind consultancy Omexom Renewable Energies Offshore. This project was funded by the German Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy from 2018 to 2022 and involved the development of a fully automatic research unit to collect information on the operation, optimisation, environmental impact, and safety aspects of AWE systems (SkyPower100 2022). Other universities and research institutes working on wind energy, lightweight design and mechatronics include RWTH Aachen and the University of Stuttgart, both of which are members of the Airborne Wind Europe association. AWE development can strengthen both the renewable energy research landscape in Germany and the diffusion of innovation in the economy.

The latter is also connected to the fact that most current AWE developers are start-ups or small enterprises, often created as spin-offs from institutions such as TU Delft or TU Berlin. AWE developers and AWE supply chains still represent niche sectors at the intersection of research and industrial implementation. **The development of AWE supply chains provides opportunities for new start-ups,** as well as enabling existing companies to diversify into high-tech clean energy markets.

Control systems are a crucial component of AWE technologies. AWE systems operate autonomously, adjusting the kite's position depending on wind conditions, the situation in the electricity market, and the potential need to evade other aircraft. This requires advanced control algorithms, real-time monitoring and predictive maintenance supported by AI. This creates opportunities for Germany's IT and electronics sectors to collaborate on developing digital innovations. Such advances could also be applied to drones, logistics, and autonomous vehicles, thereby creating spillovers and strengthening Germany's digital economy.

4.2.3 Energy security and resilience

Germany's transition towards climate neutrality is transforming the country's energy system. There are various scenarios for the future development of the German energy system, particularly with regard to electricity generation. Some focus on realistic scenarios based on current trends and existing policies (DNV 2025), while others investigate what the transformation should look like to achieve

climate neutrality by 2045 (Frömel, et al. 2025, Kopernikus-Projekt Ariadne 2021, Samadi 2022). Both types of study highlight two key developments in electricity generation:

- Electricity generation will need to grow substantially by 2045, driven by the electrification of transport, buildings and industry. Most studies expect it to more than double.
- Given the availability of mature zero-carbon electricity generation technologies, the electricity sector must fully decarbonise in order to meet climate targets. This implies that electricity generation must be based entirely on renewable energy sources.⁸

Within this policy and technical landscape, **renewable technologies such as AWE would be essential contributors to energy security**. AWE possesses several unique properties that distinguish it from conventional wind turbines and solar PV systems.

One of its most important features is its relatively **high capacity factor**⁹. In Germany, solar PV systems typically achieve a capacity factor of between 11% and 15% (Kost, et al. 2024), reflecting their inability to generate electricity at night and their reduced output during the winter. Depending on their location, onshore wind turbines achieve capacity factors of between 21% in inland Germany and 37% in wind-rich coastal regions in the north of the country. Offshore wind can reach capacity factors of between 37% and 51% (Kost, et al. 2024). Estimates put AWE's capacity factor somewhere between 35% and 50%, or even higher in high-wind areas (Weber, et al. 2021, Malz, et al. 2022, Zillmann and Bechtle 2018). This puts it on par with offshore wind energy, even in inland Germany, and well above solar PV. This makes AWE a sensible option in terms of energy supply, especially in locations where conventional wind turbines cannot be deployed. By providing a stable and decentralised electricity supply, AWE could also potentially reduce the need for grid expansion, thereby contributing to the system's overall cost-efficiency.

In addition to its capacity factor, AWE also benefits from **lower variability** (Vos, et al. 2024). The stronger, more stable winds at higher altitudes enable AWE systems to generate electricity with fewer fluctuations, putting them close to baseload power generation. Furthermore, AWE systems can adjust the position of the kites within the tether radius to capture the best winds, which fixed wind turbines

⁸ There is debate about the potential of gas-fired power generation with carbon capture, utilisation and storage (CCUS) (CDU, CSU & SPD 2025, Stratmann 2025). However, CCUS is energy-intensive, cannot capture all emissions, and is not yet scalable. It is therefore better suited to hard-to-abate sectors (e.g. cement production), alongside emission sinks (e.g. forests, moors, direct air capture) to offset residual emissions.

⁹ The capacity factor describes how much of the time during a typical year a power plant produces electricity at full capacity. This theoretical indicator effectively normalises production times below full capacity to provide a comparable measure of expected electricity generation from a unit of capacity across different technologies.

cannot do. This adaptability reduces variability further and lessens the burden on balancing mechanisms and storage solutions.

In addition, AWE offers considerable **flexibility**. Operators can adjust the output by changing the altitude of the kite, the radius of operation and kite position in the wind, or even the size of the kite itself. Seasonal optimisation through kite replacement further enhances this flexibility, enabling operators to adapt to changing weather patterns and demand cycles. In this respect, AWE's capabilities lie somewhere between those of conventional renewables, such as wind turbines and solar PV, and those of conventional thermal plants, in that it can provide both baseload and flexible generation. It can therefore speed up the energy transition by complementing other variable renewable energy sources and increasing the overall technical potential of renewables.

Another important aspect is the **alignment with seasonal demand fluctuations**. As with conventional wind power and unlike solar PV, AWE tends to generate more electricity in winter, when demand for heating and lighting is higher. This seasonal alignment reduces the need for expensive long-term storage solutions. It also facilitates sector coupling as the demand for electricity from electric mobility and heat pumps increases.

Finally, AWE systems are **highly versatile**. They can be installed in remote or mountainous areas where the use of conventional turbines may be unfeasible due to logistical issues. This decentralises the electricity supply and reduces the need for extensive grid expansion. Furthermore, their relatively small size and light weight mean they can be deployed and relocated quickly, which is highly valued in certain markets (Weber, et al. 2021). In fact, this versatility may support the creation of an entirely new market segment in wind energy with rental or leasing schemes for AWE devices (European Commission 2025).

The system-level characteristics of AWE directly impact Germany's energy security. **By incorporating a renewable energy source that offers high capacity factors, reduced variability and flexible generation options, AWE helps to diversify the electricity mix.** This reduces dependence on any single technology, thereby enhancing the system's overall resilience. Furthermore, AWE's potential for decentralised and mobile deployment reduces regional vulnerabilities and grid bottlenecks. In times of system stress, AWE's ability to provide steady and flexible electricity generation ensures that Germany can maintain a reliable supply as it transitions fully to renewable energy.

While these characteristics are important for AWE's technical contribution to the German energy system, another important factor is the cost at which AWE can deliver electricity. The **levelised cost of energy (LCOE)** is a useful metric for consistently comparing the costs of different electricity generation technologies. This metric expresses the average cost of producing one unit of electricity (e.g. in

EUR/MWh) over the lifetime of a power plant. It takes into account all relevant expenses, such as capital investment, financing, operation and maintenance, fuel (if applicable) and decommissioning. By dividing these lifetime costs by the total amount of electricity expected to be generated, the LCOE enables policymakers and investors to assess the cost-effectiveness of different technologies under given conditions.

The LCOE of renewable energy systems is particularly sensitive to the capacity factor and the scale at which they are deployed. For AWE, which has higher maintenance costs than conventional wind turbines, the durability and replacement cycle of tethers and kites are also crucial factors. As this technology matures and benefits from economies of scale, learning effects and industrial integration, its LCOE is expected to decrease, thus improving its competitiveness against established renewable energy sources such as solar PV and conventional wind.

As AWE is in its early stages of development and involves the deployment of a wide range of small-scale designs, estimates of the LCOE vary considerably in terms of current levels and possible future developments. The sector representatives in Europe currently put the LCOE of AWE at around 200 EUR/MWh. This is still significantly higher than the range for offshore wind (60–134 EUR/MWh), utility-scale solar PV with storage (43–112 EUR/MWh) and onshore wind with storage (38–105 EUR/MWh)¹⁰. Through optimisation and scaling, AWE is expected to achieve an LCOE of 25–30 EUR/MWh by 2030 (Salari, Zabihi and Murphy 2025). If this is achieved, **AWE could become a highly competitive renewable electricity technology**, reaching the same level as utility-scale solar PV and onshore wind, even without storage.

5. Conclusion

Airborne wind energy could deliver substantial economic benefits to Germany while contributing positively to the energy transition. Investment in this technology would expand the domestic portfolio of renewable generation options and stimulate industrial activity across several strategically important sectors, such as the production of electrical components, machinery, and transport/aviation technologies. Germany already enjoys a strong competitive position in these sectors. By anchoring the development of AWE within these sectors, the country could create high-quality jobs and secure long-term industrial activity. This study's assessment suggests that building an AWE industry domestically could support around 13,300 jobs and generate approximately EUR 1.3 billion in gross value added per gigawatt of installed capacity. Depending on the AWE development path, the cumulative value-added

¹⁰ Calculated from Lazard (2025) using the current exchange rate of 1 USD = 0.86 EUR.

effect could reach between EUR 3.1 billion and EUR 10.5 billion over the next ten years. Consistent expansion in Germany could also secure 30,600-104,300 job-years, or an average of 3,100-10,400 jobs, over the next ten years through multiplier effects along supply chains. At the upper range, the impact is comparable to the direct, indirect and induced employment effects of onshore wind energy in wind-rich Schleswig-Holstein in 2018 (Figure 5-1). Recurring demand for operation and maintenance ensures that this effect is not confined to the installation phase, with value and employment creation continuing over the entire system lifetime.

Figure 5-1: Potential AWE jobs compared to the job effects of onshore wind in Schleswig-Holstein

Source: DIW Econ.

From an energy security perspective, AWE complements the existing mix of wind and solar technologies by overcoming some of their most significant limitations. Its higher capacity factors, better alignment with seasonal demand and operational flexibility allow it to contribute to system stability and resilience in ways that conventional renewables cannot achieve alone. In the future, when the German power system is expected to more than double in size and operate entirely on renewable sources, such characteristics will become strategically essential. AWE could reduce the need for costly storage and ‘overcapacity’ of solar PV and wind turbines, enabling more decentralised electricity generation, particularly in areas where conventional renewables are difficult to install.

Beyond its technical and economic contributions, AWE also plays an important role in Germany’s innovation landscape. Spanning aerospace, robotics, materials science, and power engineering, the technology acts as a bridge between different fields of expertise, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and generating knowledge spillovers that can benefit other high-tech industries. It provides a fertile environment for start-ups and spin-offs, strengthening the research ecosystem through partnerships with universities and research institutes.

However, realising this potential will require a favourable institutional environment. This includes establishing clear regulatory frameworks for airborne systems, implementing supportive policies for research, demonstration and scaling up, and providing targeted incentives to encourage domestic manufacturing and the development of the supply chain. Dedicated testbeds and demonstration projects can boost visibility and investor confidence, and integrating AWE into broader energy and industrial strategies will ensure long-term stability. Aligning industrial, energy, and innovation policies would enable Germany to establish a domestic AWE industry, capturing the economic and strategic benefits of this emerging technology.

In summary, AWE provides Germany with the opportunity to improve its renewable energy mix and energy security, as well as strengthening its industrial base and innovation system. With early, well-designed support, AWE could become a cornerstone of a resilient, sustainable and competitive energy future.

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Annex A. Overview of AWE technologies

In terms of power generation, AWE systems can be classified in ground-gen and fly-gen technologies:

- **Ground-gen** systems produce electricity at the ground station. In these designs, a kite or wing pulls on a tether connected to a drum or winch on the ground, which drives a generator. Energy is produced during the reel-out phase, while energy expenditure is minimised during the reel-in phase by flying the kite in a low-lift configuration. Having heavy components, such as generators and converters, located on the ground simplifies the airborne design and maintenance of ground-gen systems.
- **Fly-gen** systems position generators directly on the airborne device. These systems typically involve turbines mounted on the kite that generate electricity directly in the air. Power is then transmitted to the ground via a conductive tether. While this approach reduces the need for large moving parts on the ground, it requires lightweight materials especially for the generators. Although the airborne devices are heavier, they can enable continuous power generation, eliminating the cyclical reel-in and reel-out phases characteristic of ground-gen systems.

Another important distinction is the flight trajectory of the kite.

- **Crosswind systems** are the most common, with the kite flying fast figure-of-eight or circular patterns perpendicular to the prevailing wind. This configuration significantly increases the apparent wind speed at the kite, thereby boosting power output.
- **Tether-aligned systems** keep the kite more directly aligned with the wind direction, generating lift and pulling power without the need for rapid crosswind manoeuvres. While generally less powerful, these systems are simpler to control and may offer advantages in terms of stability and reliability.
- **Rotational systems** employ multiple kites or blades attached to a looped tether or a carousel-like structure that rotates under the force of the wind, driving a generator. The tethers are usually kept in tension by a lifter kite.

Finally, AWE systems differ in terms of the airborne wing or kite design they use.

- **Soft kites** are lightweight, relatively inexpensive and flexible. They can be repaired by replacing individual sections, which reduces maintenance costs. However, they are less rigid in shape, which leads to lower aerodynamic efficiency and shorter lifetimes.
- **Semi-rigid kites** combine soft covers with a lightweight exoskeleton to offer a balance between flexibility and efficiency. While they are more durable than soft kites, the soft covers must be

replaced regularly, and the exoskeletons may require replacing after five to six years (Coutinho 2024).

- **Rigid wings**, comparable to those of small aircraft, provide the highest aerodynamic performance and durability. They are particularly suitable for fly-gen systems, where onboard turbines demand stability and structural integrity. However, they are heavier and more costly, with higher material and manufacturing requirements.

Figure A-1 provides an overview of the various AWE technologies, extending the classification of kite designs to how they become airborne.

Figure A-1: Overview of AWE technologies

Note: GS stands for ground station.

Source: Weber et al. (2021).